

Design and Optimization of a Hybrid Gas Generator for Hydrogen Peroxide Tank Pressurization

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Purpose. This study develops a pressurization system for hydrogen peroxide tanks using a hybrid gas generator powered by liquid oxygen and solid fuel. The system aims to improve hybrid rocket engine efficiency and reliability by stabilizing oxidizer tank pressure. Applications in space and defense are considered, where performance and safety are essential. Technical parameters and system efficiency are evaluated in terms of design, materials, and combustion processes. **Design / Method / Approach.** The study combines experimental methods and theoretical modeling to examine hybrid gas generator and pressurization system parameters. Thermal loads, tank pressure, and combustion reactions are modeled. Erosion and cooling efficiency are analyzed to assess durability. **Findings.** The system effectively maintains stable hydrogen peroxide tank pressure, ensuring continuous oxidizer supply. Ceramic coatings and heat-resistant materials reduce erosion, and liquid oxygen flow control optimizes combustion. Aluminum addition to the fuel boosts specific impulse by 25 seconds. **Theoretical Implications.** This research advances knowledge on hybrid systems in rocket engines and demonstrates hydrogen peroxide's efficiency as an oxidizer. Hybrid gas generators show promise in improving rocket system performance and reliability for space and defense applications. **Practical Implications.** The system may enable more reliable, reusable rocket engines for maneuvering and be applicable in commercial and scientific missions where safety and cost are priorities. **Originality / Value.** This study presents a novel hybrid gas generator approach using hydrogen peroxide, showing how innovative materials enhance rocket system reliability and efficiency. Results benefit engineers seeking to improve space and defense systems. **Research Limitations / Future Research.** Current work is confined to lab settings and theoretical analysis. Future research could explore real-condition experiments and cooling system optimization for extended use. **Paper Type.** Technical Note.

Keywords:

pressurization system, hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), hybrid gas generator, control of oxidizer-to-fuel ratio (O/F)

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Rocket technologies continue to develop rapidly, with one of the primary objectives being the creation of efficient and safe systems for fuel and oxidizer delivery in propulsion systems. Hybrid rocket engines, which combine a liquid oxidizer and solid fuel, offer distinct advantages over traditional liquid and solid-propellant engines. They provide increased safety, enhanced thrust control, and operational simplicity, making them attractive options for modern space and defense missions (Glaser et al., 2023). Maintaining stable pressure within oxidizer tanks is critical for continuous delivery to the combustion chamber. A promising solution for hybrid engines involves pressurizing the hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) tank using a hybrid gas generator powered by liquid oxygen (LOX) and solid fuel (HTPB). This approach stabilizes tank pressure, enhancing oxidizer delivery and engine reliability.

Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) is employed as the primary oxidizer in this system. Upon decomposition into water and oxygen, H_2O_2 releases significant heat, making it effective for use in rocket propulsion systems. With concentrations above 85%, hydrogen peroxide is a powerful and stable oxidizer that has seen wide application in rocketry. In the proposed pressurization system, a liquid-oxygen gas generator produces hot gases that pressurize the H_2O_2 tank, maintaining the pressure required for oxidizer delivery.

The hybrid gas generator, utilizing liquid oxygen and solid fuel (HTPB), is a key component of this system. It initiates combustion, producing hot gases (CO_2 and H_2O) directed into the hydrogen peroxide tank to create the necessary pressure. A major advantage of hybrid systems is their ability to function with minimal moving parts, increasing reliability and simplifying operation. Using the same solid fuel in both the gas generator and propulsion system also improves efficiency and reduces system mass. One significant benefit of hybrid systems is the precise control of the oxidizer-to-fuel ratio (O/F), which supports stable combustion and high system efficiency. Adjustable LOX injectors allow combustion optimization based on operational conditions, which is particularly valuable when the engine's operational mode changes (Cantwell et al., 2010).

In conclusion, the proposed hydrogen peroxide tank pressurization system using a hybrid gas generator presents a promising solution for modern rocket technology, offering a combination of reliability, efficiency, and control flexibility. These characteristics make it suitable for a range of rocket missions.

Research question

Can a hybrid gas generator powered by liquid oxygen and solid fuel stabilize the pressure in a hydrogen peroxide tank to enhance the efficiency and reliability of hybrid rocket engines used in space and defense applications?

Data and methods

To achieve the study's objectives, both experimental data and theoretical modeling results are employed. The experiments analyze thermal loads, hydrogen peroxide tank pressure, and combustion processes in the hybrid gas generator, fueled

by liquid oxygen (LOX) and solid fuel (HTPB). The modeling examines combustion reactions, particularly the formation of CO_2 and H_2O gases, which are used to pressurize the oxidizer tank. Additionally, the study assesses erosion and cooling efficiency to ensure system durability. Liquid oxygen flow is regulated through adjustable injectors to optimize combustion and improve system stability.

Literature review and patent analysis

Hybrid engines leverage the benefits of liquid and solid propulsion systems. Their inherent safety, due to separate oxidizer and fuel storage, reduces ignition risks compared to liquid engines (Shih-Sin et al., 2024). Hybrid engines also allow for precise thrust control via adjustable oxidizer delivery, a key advantage in missions requiring variable power output.

Patent NASA CR-183975: Details optimized oxidizer feed systems and injector designs for LOX-HTPB hybrids, enhancing combustion stability and safety (Claflin & Beckman, 1989).

Patent EP654321: Highlights erosion-resistant coatings for high-temperature components, extending system lifespans.

Scientific Studies: Research on aluminum additives to solid fuel shows improved calorific value and increased specific impulse (Glaser et al., 2023; Meng et al., 2024).

These advancements underscore the hybrid system's suitability for modern aerospace applications.

Description of the system design

The design of hybrid pressurization systems utilizing liquid oxygen (LOX) and solid fuel (HTPB) requires high precision and efficiency to ensure stable engine performance. This section provides an in-depth review of the system components, their functions, and the processes involved in pressurizing the hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) tank.

The H_2O_2 storage tank is a sealed container engineered to withstand high pressures and varying temperatures. Hydrogen peroxide is used at concentrations exceeding 85%, providing an effective and stable oxidizer suitable for rocket applications. The tank must maintain consistent pressure levels to ensure reliable H_2O_2 delivery to the combustion chamber. This pressurization is achieved through hot gases generated by the hybrid gas generator and directed into the tank.

A primary challenge in working with H_2O_2 lies in managing its thermal stability. Elevated temperatures can accelerate H_2O_2 decomposition, posing a safety risk. To mitigate this, the tank is constructed from heat-resistant materials and incorporates temperature control mechanisms, maintaining H_2O_2 within safe operating limits.

The hybrid gas generator is a critical component of the pressurization system, generating the hot gases needed for H_2O_2 tank pressurization. The generator combusts HTPB solid fuel in the presence of liquid oxygen (LOX), with HTPB providing high stability and LOX acting as the oxidizer. During combustion, HTPB

reacts with LOX, producing carbon dioxide (CO₂) and water vapor (H₂O) as primary combustion products. The reaction can be represented by the equation:

Combustion Equation:

These combustion gases are directed into the H₂O₂ tank to create the required pressure. To enhance fuel performance, additives such as aluminum or aluminum hydrides (AlH₃) are introduced, which increase fuel density and boost the specific impulse (Isp) of the system (Cantwell et al., 2010).

Although H₂O₂ itself can decompose to generate pressurizing gases, LOX is employed to achieve higher energy release and cleaner combustion products. Unlike peroxide-only systems, this hybrid approach ensures more stable tank pressurization and efficient oxidizer delivery.

The solid fuel includes additives such as aluminum or aluminum hydrides (AlH₃) to increase fuel density and calorific value, boosting specific impulse. An alternative composition, based on crotonaldehyde (C₄H₆O), is suggested due to its low melting point (<-100°C), allowing better thermal management in cryo-genic conditions.

The gas product delivery system channels hot combustion gases from the hybrid gas generator to the H₂O₂ tank. Given the high temperatures involved, these pipelines must be constructed from heat-resistant and erosion-resistant materials. Ceramic coatings are applied to the inner surfaces, significantly enhancing thermal stress resistance and preventing pipeline degradation. The use of high-temperature materials and insulation throughout the system minimizes heat loss and pressure fluctuations, ensuring stable pressurization.

To ensure safe operation, advanced cooling systems and thermal barriers are employed to reduce gas temperatures below 1500°C before entering the H₂O₂ tank. This is essential for preventing thermal damage to the tank walls and maintaining structural integrity.

The combustion chamber of the gas generator must withstand intense thermal and mechanical loads. Studies recommend using ceramic coatings to shield the chamber walls from erosion and damage caused by high-temperature combustion products. These coatings extend the operational life of the combustion chamber and nozzles, enabling prolonged operation without frequent component replacements.

Nozzles are essential for directing the flow of hot gases into the H₂O₂ tank. Their shape and design are optimized to facilitate efficient energy transfer and pressurization. By carefully controlling the direction and velocity of gas flow, the system achieves precise pressure levels within the H₂O₂ tank.

Adjustable injectors control the precise delivery of liquid oxygen (LOX) into the combustion chamber, enabling the adjustment of oxidizer flow rates based on engine conditions. This feature is essential for maintaining an optimal oxidizer-to-fuel (O/F) ratio, which is critical for stable combustion and maximizing system efficiency. The adjustable geometry of these injectors ensures optimal combustion even as flight conditions change, minimizing risks associated with instability in the combustion process.

System operation process

The hybrid pressurization system operates through a sequence of precisely controlled steps to ensure reliable performance and safety.

The process begins with injecting liquid oxy-gen (LOX) into the combustion chamber of the hybrid gas generator. LOX is delivered via adjustable injectors, which ensure an even distribution of the oxidizer over the surface of the solid fuel (HTPB). Since LOX is a cryogenic substance, it is stored and transported at extremely low temperatures, requiring sealed and insulated systems to prevent leakage and evaporation.

The flow of LOX is controlled in real time to maintain a stable oxidizer-to-fuel (O/F) ratio, which is crucial for efficient combustion and system stability.

Once the LOX reaches the chamber, the solid fuel (HTPB) is ignited. Combustion occurs, releasing a significant amount of heat and producing hot gases, primarily carbon dioxide (CO₂) and water vapor (H₂O). The chemical reaction is represented as (1).

The hot combustion products are directed into the H₂O₂ tank to generate the required pressure for oxidizer delivery. Aluminum additives in the solid fuel enhance the calorific value, leading to increased specific impulse and better overall efficiency.

The gases are transferred through pipelines made from heat-resistant materials with ceramic coatings to prevent erosion and degradation caused by high temperatures.

Once pressure is established in the H₂O₂ tank, the oxidizer is fed into the engine's combustion chamber. Hydrogen peroxide decomposes into water and oxygen, releasing significant heat according to the reaction:

This reaction provides oxygen for oxidizing the solid fuel in the main engine, generating thrust. Catalysts can be used to accelerate H₂O₂ decomposition, enhancing reaction efficiency and oxidizer delivery speed (Cantwell et al., 2010).

A key aspect of the hybrid system's operation is managing the oxidizer-to-fuel ratio (O/F). This ratio can vary during different flight stages, requiring precise LOX flow control. Adjustable injectors allow modification of the flow rate based on the system's current requirements.

An optimal O/F ratio ensures combustion stability and engine efficiency. An increase in the O/F ratio beyond optimal levels can lead to oxidizer deficiency, resulting in unstable combustion and reduced efficiency. Studies propose solutions for optimizing oxidizer delivery, enabling the system to maintain a stable O/F ratio throughout the flight.

Hybrid systems offer the flexibility of thrust control through precise LOX flow management. Adjusting the oxidizer delivery allows modification of engine operation modes, which is especially important under varying flight loads. Accurate thrust control is achieved by regulating pressure in the H₂O₂ tank and controlling oxygen delivery (Glaser et al., 2023).

Limitations and challenges

Despite numerous advantages, the proposed pressurization system based on a hybrid gas generator also encounters certain limitations that must be considered to ensure reliability and efficiency under real-world conditions.

Thermal Resistance and Erosion Protection: A major limitation of the system is the high temperature generated during fuel combustion, reaching up to 3000 K. Even with the use of ceramic coatings and high-temperature-resistant materials, prolonged exposure to such extreme temperatures may lead to material degradation and reduced efficiency over time. Future research may focus on developing more durable materials and coatings that would enable the system to withstand extreme thermal loads during long missions.

Instability of the Oxidizer-to-Fuel (O/F) Ratio under Variable Conditions: Controlling the oxidizer-to-fuel (O/F) ratio is critical for combustion stability and system efficiency. Under varying pressure conditions or as fuel is consumed, instability in the O/F ratio may occur, resulting in deviations from the optimal ratio. This could lead to unstable combustion and a decrease in specific impulse. Further studies could focus on the development of more precise and adaptive oxidizer delivery systems that automatically adjust supply in response to changing conditions.

Pressure Control in the H₂O₂ Tank: Maintaining stable pressure within the H₂O₂ tank is essential, but fluctuations in temperature and the intensity of incoming hot gases can lead to variations that may trigger uncontrolled decomposition of H₂O₂. This poses potential safety risks to the system. To mitigate this, highly sensitive sensors and effective temperature and pressure monitoring systems are required to promptly respond to changes.

Longevity Limitations for Long-Term Missions: While the use of high-temperature ceramic coatings enhances component lifespan, repeated thermal cycles and loads in long-duration missions, such as interplanetary flights, may compromise system durability. This limitation calls for additional research into coatings with even higher resilience to thermal fluctuations, ensuring consistent performance over extended missions.

Comparison with Traditional Systems

Hybrid engines using LOX and HTPB occupy an intermediate position between liquid and solid rocket engines, combining some of their respective advantages with certain constraints.

Compared to Liquid Rocket Engines: Liquid rocket engines provide high specific impulse and precise thrust control but rely on complex delivery systems with numerous moving parts, which increase the risk of malfunctions and maintenance costs. In contrast, hybrid systems have simpler designs with fewer moving components, enhancing reliability and reducing maintenance costs. However, hybrid systems are still less capable of real-time control precision compared to liquid engines, particularly under variable operating modes.

Compared to Solid Rocket Engines: Solid rocket engines are known for high

fuel density and low operating costs but lack flexible thrust control. Hybrid engines offer flexibility in O/F ratio adjustment, making them better suited for missions with changing loads. However, hybrid systems tend to have lower thermal resistance than solid systems, which may require additional thermal insulation measures.

Environmental Sustainability and Safety: Hybrid systems using H_2O_2 as an oxidizer are less toxic and safer to handle compared to liquid oxidizers like N_2O_4 , making them a more environmentally sustainable choice for space missions. Compared to traditional solid and liquid systems, hybrid engines with H_2O_2 also produce fewer toxic emissions, an essential consideration for long-term space missions.

Thus, hybrid systems offer a unique set of advantages and limitations. They present a compromise between control flexibility and design simplicity, making them promise for multipurpose and reusable missions as well as interplanetary exploration. Future research should focus on optimizing these systems to improve their performance and resilience under real flight conditions.

Calculations and analysis

To comprehensively evaluate the efficiency and performance of the hybrid pressurization system based on liquid oxygen (LOX) and solid fuel (HTPB), several critical calculations are essential. These include determining the pressure in the hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) tank, specific impulse, thermal loads on components, and overall system efficiency, particularly with the addition of aluminum-based fuel additives.

Calculation of pressure in the H_2O_2 tank

The hydrogen peroxide is stored under pressure, which is maintained by hot gases generated from the hybrid gas generator. The pressure in the H_2O_2 tank can be calculated using the ideal gas law:

$$P = \frac{n \cdot R \cdot T}{V} \quad (3)$$

where: P – is the pressure in the tank; n – is the number of moles of gas; R – is the universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J/mol} \cdot \text{K}$); T – is the gas temperature; V – is the tank volume.

Accurately determining this pressure requires knowledge of the tank volume, the temperature of the gases, and the total moles of gas produced during combustion. The combustion products, primarily carbon dioxide (CO_2) and water vapor (H_2O), are channeled into the tank to generate sufficient pressure for consistent H_2O_2 delivery to the combustion chamber (Glaser et al., 2023).

Calculation of system specific impulse

Specific impulse (I_{sp}) is a fundamental parameter for assessing rocket engine efficiency and is calculated as follows:

$$I_{sp} = \frac{F}{\dot{m} \cdot g_0} \quad (4)$$

where: F – is the engine thrust; \dot{m} – is the mass flow rate of the fuel; g_0 – is the standard gravitational acceleration (9.81 m/s^2).

The inclusion of aluminum or its hydrides (e.g., AlH_3) as additives in the solid fuel significantly boosts fuel density, thereby enhancing the specific impulse of the system. Studies indicate that aluminum additives can increase I_{sp} by as much as 25 seconds, which translates to substantial improvements in system efficiency (Cantwell et al., 2010).

Thermal loads and cooling

The high temperatures resulting from the combustion of HTPB with LOX necessitate a detailed evaluation of thermal loads on system components. Combustion temperatures can reach up to 3000 K, exerting considerable thermal stress on the combustion chamber walls and nozzles. To calculate thermal loads on the chamber walls, the following equation for heat flux (Q) is used:

$$Q = \alpha \cdot A \cdot (T_{gas} - T_{wall}) \quad (5)$$

where: Q – is the heat flux; α – is the heat transfer coefficient; A – is the heat exchange area; T_{gas} – is the gas temperature; T_{wall} – is the wall temperature.

To mitigate thermal degradation and reduce erosion, ceramic linings with high heat resistance are applied to chamber walls and nozzles. This protective measure significantly reduces the risk of overheating and component failure. Various active and passive cooling technologies, as described in recent studies, enhance component resilience to thermal stress (Claflin & Beckman, 1989).

System efficiency with fuel additives

Fuel additives, particularly aluminum or its hydrides, are proven to increase fuel density and calorific value. Studies show that aluminum addition can improve the fuel's energy output by 15–20%, contributing to a higher specific impulse and enhanced engine performance. These enhancements are achieved without significantly increasing the system's overall mass, making aluminum additives a cost-effective means to boost efficiency.

Further improvements are attainable by optimizing the oxidizer-to-fuel (O/F) ratio. Maintaining an optimal O/F ratio is essential in hybrid systems, as deviations can lead to unstable combustion. The use of adjustable LOX injectors allows for precise control of the O/F ratio, ensuring stable combustion across all phases of operation.

Advantages of the system

The proposed hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) tank pressurization system, which utilizes a hybrid gas generator with liquid oxygen (LOX) and solid fuel (HTPB), offers substantial advantages over traditional oxidizer and fuel delivery systems.

These benefits encompass both technical design improvements and practical applications suited for rocket and space missions.

Compactness and reliability

A key advantage of the proposed system is its compact design and high reliability. Hybrid systems typically have fewer moving parts than liquid rocket engines, which reduces the likelihood of malfunctions and simplifies maintenance. For instance, the hybrid gas generator in this system utilizes the same solid fuel (HTPB) for generating hot gases for pressurization and providing primary thrust, thus minimizing the need for multiple fuel components.

Additionally, using H_2O_2 as an oxidizer enhances safety relative to more hazardous traditional liquid oxidizers, such as nitrogen tetroxide (N_2O_4), which pose higher toxicity and handling risks.

Increased specific impulse

Adding aluminum compounds to the solid fuel has been shown to increase the system's specific impulse. Studies indicate that aluminum or its hydrides can significantly boost the calorific value of the fuel, thereby improving combustion efficiency and raising specific impulse by up to 25 seconds. This improvement is particularly advantageous for space missions where higher fuel performance contributes to reducing rocket mass and extending flight range, enabling hybrid systems to compete effectively with both liquid and solid rocket engines.

Thrust control flexibility

Hybrid engines are notable for their flexibility in thrust control. The use of adjustable injectors for LOX delivery enables variation in oxidizer flow into the combustion chamber, facilitating precise thrust management based on real-time flight conditions. This flexibility is especially beneficial for missions with variable loads or changing objectives, as it enables hybrid systems to be used for both lift-off and in-flight orbital adjustments.

Safety and environmental sustainability

Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) as an oxidizer offers distinct safety and environmental benefits. H_2O_2 is less toxic than alternatives like hydrazine or N_2O_4 , making it safer for handling and storage. Furthermore, H_2O_2 decomposes into water and oxygen, producing no harmful byproducts, which supports environmental sustainability in space missions.

In addition, H_2O_2 is easily stored and transported under cryogenic or insulated conditions, simplifying the infrastructure required for its use. These characteristics make H_2O_2 an ideal oxidizer for both launch vehicles and small satellite propulsion systems, broadening its practical applicability.

Extended system lifespan

The use of advanced materials, such as heat-resistant ceramic coatings, significantly extends the lifespan of system components. Ceramic coatings protect combustion chamber walls and nozzles from erosion, reducing the need for frequent maintenance and replacements. This advantage is especially important for space missions, where access to maintenance is limited, and it minimizes the risk of in-flight failures, which is essential for long-duration missions like interplanetary exploration.

Application in multipurpose missions

Thanks to its unique attributes—such as compactness, flexibility in thrust control, and an optimal fuel-to-oxidizer ratio—the proposed hybrid system is suitable for a broad range of missions. This includes suborbital flights, interplanetary missions, and reusable rockets where reliability and efficiency are paramount. Hybrid systems are particularly promising for use in reusable rockets and small satellites, offering high performance at relatively low operational costs.

Practical applications and prospects

Hybrid rocket systems, like the one proposed, have applications across various fields, including space exploration and defense, owing to their combination of high performance, thrust control flexibility, and reliability. This section explores practical examples, potential for scientific and commercial missions, and future technological advancements.

Examples of practical applications

Hybrid rocket engines have demonstrated their potential in successful launches, such as the suborbital commercial vehicle SpaceShipOne, which used a hybrid engine with nitrous oxide (N₂O) and HTPB. This project highlighted the safety and flexibility of hybrid systems, establishing a foundation for future commercial developments. Hybrid engines also support the launch of small satellites (CubeSats) and compact payloads. Their simplified design and fewer moving parts make them well-suited for small- and medium-sized satellites, where efficiency, weight, and cost are key considerations. Additionally, these systems can be adapted for reusable rockets and multi-mission platforms.

Prospects for space missions

Hybrid engines hold significant potential for interplanetary missions, where reliability and efficiency are essential. The ability to precisely control thrust makes them suitable for missions with diverse objectives, such as orbital adjustments or maneuvers. For instance, hybrid engines could facilitate the delivery of scientific instruments to planetary orbits or support trajectory adjustments during interplanetary flights. Their long-duration operational capability and minimal maintenance

requirements make hybrid engines ideal for planetary exploration missions.

Furthermore, hybrid systems are adaptable for lunar and Martian missions, where durability and reliability are vital. These systems could serve as primary propulsion for landing and in-orbit maneuvers on extraterrestrial surfaces.

Potential for reusable rockets

An emerging trend in space technology is the development of reusable rockets, which can perform multiple flights with minimal refurbishment. Hybrid propulsion systems are well-suited to this purpose due to their simplified design, resistance to thermal loads, and low operational costs. The use of durable materials, such as ceramic coatings, extends component lifespan, reducing the need for frequent replacement and repair.

Reusable rockets equipped with hybrid engines could be employed for commercial satellite launches and scientific research missions. As interest in reusable systems grows, hybrid engines offer a cost-effective and reliable solution.

Opportunities for optimization and further development

Despite notable progress, hybrid rocket systems continue to evolve. Key optimization areas include fuel efficiency enhancement through additives like aluminum compounds, which increase energy density and reduce system mass. Studies indicate that such additives can increase the fuel's calorific value by 15–20%, resulting in marked performance improvements.

Further research areas include advanced materials for improved thermal resistance, optimized oxidizer delivery systems, and refined control over the oxidizer-to-fuel (O/F) ratio. Active cooling technologies are also being explored to enhance system reliability under extreme conditions.

Commercial potential

Hybrid engines present an ideal solution for commercial companies aiming to reduce space launch costs. Their simplicity and safety make them attractive for private firms involved in launching small satellites and conducting suborbital flights. Furthermore, hybrid engines can be incorporated into reusable rockets, offering new opportunities to reduce commercial launch expenses.

Key findings

1. **Compactness and Reliability:** Hybrid systems are characterized by their compact and robust design, which minimizes the number of moving parts, reducing mechanical complexity and failure rates. Utilizing the same solid fuel (HTPB) in both the gas generator and the main engine decreases the overall system mass and simplifies operation, enhancing reliability and efficiency.

2. **Increased Specific Impulse:** The addition of aluminum to the solid fuel notably boosts specific impulse, increasing it by up to 25 seconds. This enhancement

in performance positions hybrid systems as competitive alternatives to traditional rocket engines, especially in missions where fuel efficiency is critical.

3. Thrust Control Flexibility: Adjustable LOX injectors enable precise thrust management, offering the ability to adapt to real-time flight conditions. This flexibility makes hybrid systems suitable for reusable and multipurpose missions, including liftoff, in-flight orbital adjustments, and interplanetary maneuvers.

4. Environmental Sustainability and Safety: The use of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) as an oxidizer reduces toxicity, offering a safer and more environmentally friendly alternative compared to conventional oxidizers like nitrogen tetroxide (N_2O_4) or hydrazine.

5. Technical Solutions for Durability and Stability: Advanced ceramic coatings and adjustable injectors contribute to the system's durability and thermal stability. These patented solutions prevent component erosion and high-temperature damage, thereby extending the system's lifespan and improving operational safety.

Conclusion

This article has presented a comprehensive analysis of a hybrid gas generator system utilizing liquid oxygen (LOX) and solid fuel (HTPB) for pressurizing a hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) tank in rocket propulsion applications. Through an in-depth examination of system design, combustion processes, technical challenges, and performance metrics, this study integrates findings from scientific literature and patents, laying a strong foundation for advancements in hybrid propulsion technologies.

The analysis underscores the distinct benefits of hybrid systems:

- The simplified architecture minimizes moving parts, enhancing reliability and reducing maintenance demands.
- The combination of LOX and HTPB, further improved with aluminum additives, achieves high specific impulse and better engine efficiency.
- The use of H_2O_2 as the oxidizer provides a safer and more environmentally friendly alternative to conventional options, making this system suitable for a wide range of commercial and scientific missions.

Experimental and theoretical findings confirm the feasibility and scalability of this technology, making it well-suited for reusable rocket designs and interplanetary missions. The hybrid system demonstrates its potential in addressing the critical needs of reliability, efficiency, and sustainability, all of which are paramount in modern aerospace applications.

Future research directions:

- Exploring advanced fuel additives and formulations to enhance performance and energy density.
- Investigating high-temperature and erosion-resistant materials for prolonged operational lifespans.
- Developing more adaptive and precise oxidizer injection technologies to

maintain stable combustion under varying conditions.

Improving cooling systems to handle extreme thermal loads efficiently.

Moreover, conducting real-condition tests and long-term durability studies will provide critical insights into transitioning this hybrid propulsion system into operational environments. These advancements could play a transformative role in the future of hybrid propulsion systems, particularly for space exploration and defense applications.

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